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Artificial Intelligence for mass Democratic Deliberations: The AI4Deliberation project Objectives and Methodology

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Abstract. Democracy is facing challenges including loss of trust in institutions, disillusionment and declining interest among citizens, increasing political polarisation, online disinformation and politically manipulated information, and a growing distance between citizens and elected representatives. This can change if proper deliberative processes and tools are institutionalised that exploit the rapid advances in Artificial Intelligence and citizens’ post-Covid competencies. The next generation of digital deliberations could be grounded on solid democracy theory, multimodal, usable and accessible, gamified, mass, enabled by the novel but also legal and ethical AI features, and easily adopted and institutionalized. In this context, the AI4Deliberation project aims to provide robust, ethical AI tools and comprehensive guidance to assist governments in institutionalising, using and evaluating multimodal, gamified, mass deliberations. In this paper, we present the project’s objectives, approach, pilots, expected results, and impact.

Keywords: AI, mass deliberation, AI4Deliberation

1 Introduction

Democracy is declining worldwide after constant growth in last century’s last quarter. Democracy cannot be taken for granted as it faces challenges including a loss of trust in EU institutions, disillusionment and declining interest among citizens, increasing political polarisation, online disinformation and politically manipulated information, and a growing distance between citizens and elected representatives¹ [1]. To face these challenges, according to the European Commission, we need to “*promote and protect a civic space where an active and independent civil society and citizens are provided with the enabling conditions and tools to become more engaged*” [2]. But how would this

¹According to the Eurobarometer 92% of EU citizens want their voices to be better taken into account, 89% say democracy needs strengthening and 65% feel they cannot make a difference in politics. Although much has been done for this challenge (e.g., European Citizens’ Panels), citizens feel that more is needed.

space look like, what *tools* it must include and how would citizens become more *engaged*?

Democracy is based on dialogue and deliberation between equal citizens. In participatory democracy, citizens have the opportunity to be involved in decision-making on matters affecting their lives. Online participation is facilitating mass participation however there is ample empirical evidence that online participation platforms suffer from low participation, opaque processes, and low-quality citizen contributions. In deliberative democracy, everyone is given the equal opportunity to express their opinion. Deliberative processes are structured and allow time for understanding the discussion topic, providing positions and arguments, and reaching a consensus. There is ample evidence that deliberative processes result in better policy outcomes, greater legitimacy to make hard choices, enhanced public trust in democratic institutions, empowered citizens, decreased corruption; they also increase electorate accuracy reasoning [3] decreasing polarization [4] and disinformation amongst many others. A relevant good example is the recent Conference on the Future of Europe. However, implementing successful deliberative processes in practice is not equally straightforward and all kinds of bias, underrepresentation, politics, and so on are introduced resulting in unfair outcomes.

To make things more complex, the world today is considerably different than just five years ago. Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) provides unprecedented features and challenges to all human activities. AI can not only support but radically change how deliberations are conducted. In addition, after COVID-19, the vast majority of the population is accustomed to video communication via tele-conference. Communication between the young is multimodal, dominated by video (e.g. Tiktok, Instagram) and audio rather than text. Screen time has increased and is dominated by social media and gaming. Games provide interesting engaging mechanisms, e.g., by employing skill points, scoreboards and missions, which remain unexploited in democratic participation.

We envision the next generation of digital deliberations as: grounded on solid democracy theory, multimodal (video, audio, text), usable and accessible, gamified (e.g. using skill points, scoreboards, missions, and avatars), mass, enabled by novel but also legal and ethical AI features (e.g., summarisation, moderation, fact-checking, hate speech and toxicity detection) and easily adopted and institutionalized.

In this paper, the AI4Deliberation project is outlined, which aims to address the challenge of integrating AI in democratic deliberations. This is a 3-year project funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe framework.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, work in related fields is presented. In Section 3, the AI4Deliberation project is outlined. In Sections 4 and 5 the project's objectives and overall approach are presented. Section 6 summarises the four pilots that will be performed within the project while Section 7 outlines the expected results and impact. Finally, in Section 8 conclusions and future work are given.

2 Related Work

Deliberation and participation methods include deliberative polling, world cafe, citizen jury, civic lottery, citizens' initiatives reviews, Deliberative Delphi, and many others.

In the literature, there is a well-documented trade-off between deliberation (which aims to increase the quality of discussion) and participation (which aims to increase the number of participants). Several deliberation platforms already exist [5][6] e.g., DebateGraph, Polis, assembl, decidim, citizen lab, adhocracy+, loomio, delib, civocracy, fluicity, discuto, ethelo) enabling online deliberations to take place in various contexts and countries. In addition, it has been suggested that gamification (e.g. use of scoreboards, skill levels, mission and avatars) should be used to motivate civic participation [7][8].

AI and Large Language Models (LLMs) have shown promising features that can potentially benefit deliberation platforms. These include but are not limited to video understanding via Vid-LLMs, summarization, translation, NER, sentiment analysis, decision support, prediction, interactive data visualization, and video summarization. Work has already been done in applying AI and LLMs at deliberation-specific tasks such as consensus building [9], summarization/moderation at deliberation platforms [10], argument extraction [11][12], fact-checking [13], and misinformation detection [14].

The potential benefits of using AI in deliberations include operational and analytical improvements (e.g., increased efficiency, enhanced data analysis, efficient resource allocation, real-time feedback, cost savings, adaptability to changing contexts, deliberative quality check), decision-making enhancements (e.g., improved decision support, reduced human biases, transparent decision-making, integrity in decision processes), user-centric benefits (e.g., personalization, citizen empowerment, enhanced accessibility, improved inclusivity, enhanced public engagement) and data security. For example, a specific problem of digital deliberation is matching, i.e. which people should be given the opportunity to directly interact. Simple random assignment could conceivably be improved by automatically matching people with specific traits, characteristics, or concerns. Here, an AI recommender system could be applied which should respect *ethical* principles (e.g., Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI or the upcoming CoE Convention on AI, human rights, democracy and the rule of law) and *legal* regulation, such as personal data protection (e.g., GDPR provisions on profiling) and AI regulation (e.g., the EU AI Act). Also, digital deliberation carries an information problem. How can users and the moderators of the platform make sure to capture all relevant contributions and surface them to those concerned? Especially in mass participation situations this is highly challenging. Here LLMs could be applied to provide summaries of commonly held concerns, structured in issues, opinions and arguments (see IBIS model [15]), or to surface specific minority concerns otherwise at risk of remaining invisible.

Drilling down to the deliberation models and the specifics of running digital deliberation platforms will provide other, more technical, challenges that AI could conceivably be used to address. With all these applications, there come considerable ethical and technological risks and concerns. This is especially so, since posts include political statements and concerns that external service providers could conceivably use to profile and target people, which the European GDPR prohibits. Accordingly, it must be guaranteed that AI solutions are transparent, explainable, publicly interrogable, and contestable. This is an area where a *laissez-faire* black-box approach carries significant risks and must be avoided. Potential risks and concerns of the use of AI in deliberations include data bias, algorithmic bias, transparency, explainability, public trust and

perception, inclusivity, security and privacy, human-AI collaboration, resilience or technological sovereignty of the technical infrastructure, legal and regulatory compliance, education and awareness.

3 The AI4Deliberation project

The AI4Deliberation project aims to provide robust, ethical AI tools and comprehensive guidance to assist governments in institutionalising, using and evaluating multimodal, gamified, mass deliberations.

The vision of the project is to equip governments with a theoretically solid and empirically tested set of AI-enabled deliberative processes, a comprehensive framework with practical guidelines, and an AI toolkit that will enable them to design, institutionalise, operate and evaluate transparent, ethical, inclusive, multimodal, gamified, mass citizens deliberations resulting in more active and inclusive citizenship and increased trust to rule-of-law based institutions by citizens.

The focus of the AI4Deliberation on multimodal communication (including video), gamification and mass scale based on solid deliberation theories makes this project unique at a global scale and clearly distinguishes it from other deliberation projects in Europe (e.g. ITHACA, ORBIS etc.) and worldwide (e.g. Stanford Online Deliberation Platform). The AI4Deliberation is multidisciplinary as shown in fig. 1 involving political science, computer science, law and ethics.

Fig. 1. AI4Deliberation in a Nutshell

4 AI4Deliberation Objectives

The project’s main objectives are six. Each objective is divided into sub-objectives, each having an ambition, as follows:

O1. To *demystify* the role of AI in digital democratic deliberations and *elicit* needs. Specific sub-objectives include:

- To analyse and synthesise the scientific literature and practice in the cross-section of the following fields: deliberation processes and platforms, AI and LLMs (including video LLMs), argumentation mining, evaluation models.
- To map the future of multimodal AI deliberations using scenarios.
- To elicit stakeholders' needs and considerations.

The ambition is to map existing knowledge and future scenarios.

O2. To *design innovative, multimodal, gamified, AI-enabled deliberative processes* while addressing relevant *social (legal, ethical), technical, incentive and integrity challenges*. Specific sub-objectives include:

- To enhance existing deliberative methods by augmenting them with multimodal AI features and considering institutionalisation of deliberation, gamification elements for increased incentive, as well as participation culture and engagement strategies. This includes adopting deliberation quality indexes for checking the integrity of the process.
- To investigate legal and ethical aspects of multimodal AI deliberations.

The ambition is to propose new, ethical deliberation methods that exploit AI and gamification.

O3. To co-develop a *comprehensive framework* for institutionalising AI-enabled deliberations. Specific sub-objectives include:

- To identify conditions and requirements for designing and institutionalising AI-enabled deliberation.
- To gain empirical insights on the effects of institutional contexts on the enactment of AI-enabled deliberation.
- To develop a framework that prescribes the institutional context of AI-enabled deliberation in the public domain.
- To identify and facilitate investment decisions and capacity building to translate the framework to practice.

The ambition is to co-develop all needed info for institutionalising the new AI deliberation methods in the public domain and AI tools.

O4. To develop a novel *AI Toolkit* and integrate it in a *deliberation platform* that can support and advance deliberative democracy leveraging multimodal LLMs in an ethical, trustworthy and transparent way. Specific sub-objectives include:

- To identify open-source AI tools and models, including Large Language Models (LLMs) and systematically test them to determine whether and to what extent they can support deliberation activities. The focus will be on exploiting multimodal LLMs enabling the processing of various input types by citizens such as video, audio, text. If existing AI solutions (e.g., LLMs) are not adequate to support deliberative activities, we will consider fine-tuning existing AI models or training new ones.
- To develop a modular Argument Mining Framework and relevant modules addressing the unique challenges raised by large-scale deliberation data.
- To design a reusable and modular Reference Architecture for AI deliberations.

- To develop a Deliberation Knowledge Graph containing high-quality, structured deliberations data that will be the base for enhancing/training the AI models as well as for neuro-symbolic reasoning approaches.
- To enhance an open-source deliberation platform with multimodal AI features and gamification elements and to develop an app for mobile devices.

The ambition is to develop innovative AI tools to support the new deliberation methods. O5. To deploy and evaluate *real-life pilots* in four European countries under different settings and measure acceptance, trust, and usability. Specific sub-objectives include:

- To construct a model for evaluating acceptance and trust, specifically for AI deliberations, and devise a method to evaluate usability. We will gather empirical data to determine which factors contribute to acceptance and trust and which do not particularly in the use of video and gamification techniques (rewards).
- To develop a concrete evaluation plan for each pilot site.
- To pilot all our results in four real-life scenarios: (a) international pilot on Long Covid, (b) national pilot from government on legislation, (c) national pilot on climate change by an international NGO, and (d) local pilot by a German city on topics to be determined at pilot time. In addition, to conduct a citizen survey of a representative sample using a polling company.

The ambition is to illustrate the impact of the new deliberation methods, framework and AI tools for society.

O6. To develop a *sustainability plan* and *policy recommendations*. Specific sub-objectives include:

- To prepare a plan to ensure the project’s results are sustained after the end of the project.
- To issue policy briefs and recommendations on employing AI in mass deliberations for policy makers.

The ambition is to develop solid policy recommendations.

5 AI4Deliberation Approach

Figure 2 presents the overall approach of the research work to be carried out in the project. This approach is influenced by agile software development methodologies and open, deliberative, co-creation processes.

The project plans for 4 (*mega*)sprints to meet objectives O2 to O5. Each sprint will focus on a different aspect, from general to specific, thus refining, improving, and enhancing previous work. The aim at each sprint is to add more features as our confidence level increases. Work on O2 (AI deliberative processes), O3 (comprehensive framework), O4 (AI toolkit) at the beginning of each sprint will refine the work to be done and items to be delivered within the sprint. The work that will be developed within the three areas will be piloted and evaluated (O5). The overall plan is presented in figure 3 and is outlined here:

First mega-sprint: Think big and prepare. The aim is to produce the basic artefacts to provide a socio-technical “infrastructure” for the rest of the work. These will be deployed in pilot sites and tested by consortium members only. For example, in the case

of the AI toolkit, we want to investigate whether existing open-source AI solutions provide the needed deliberation features.

Fig. 2. AI4Deliberation overall approach

Second mega-sprint: Start small. The aim is to produce all artifacts needed for pilots’ administrators to set up and operate AI, multimodal, gamified deliberations and conduct small scale pilots with small number of citizens.

Third mega-sprint: Scale fast. The aim is to develop all essential artefacts to enable deploying, operating and evaluating large scale deliberations with citizens.

Fourth mega-sprint: Finalise. The aim is to finalise all the main project’s artifacts based on the evaluation results.

	AI-enabled Deliberative Processes	AI4Deliberation Comprehensive Framework	AI4Deliberation AI Toolkit	Pilots and Evaluation
1	AI-enabled Deliberation Stages	Conditions, requirements	Sandbox v1, Semantic model for KG, Architecture v1	Evaluation model Use by consortium members
2	AI-enabled Deliberation Stages and Processes	Observations, co-creation output	Sandbox v2 (fine-tuned models), Architecture, KG v2, Preliminary AI solutions for pilots	Use by consortium members and citizens
3	AI-enabled Deliberation Stages and Processes - refined	Invest. decisions, capacity building - comprehensive framework (draft)	Architecture v3, AI toolkit v1, KG v2, AI deliberation platform & app	Use by citizens in the pilot areas
4	AI-enabled Deliberation Stages and Processes - final	Investment decisions, capacity building; comprehensive framework	Final Architecture, AI toolkit, KG, AI deliberation platform & app	Ready to be used by everyone

Fig. 3. Four sprints of Research and Innovation actions

6 Pilots

In the project we will run four trial pilots carefully selected for complementarity. An overview of each pilot follows.

Pilot 1. National-level deliberations on draft legislation (opengov.gr)

In Greece, every draft law is published by the relevant Ministry in opengov.gr, usually for two weeks, for citizens to express their opinion (Fig. 4). The underlying platform is WordPress while the template design and source code is available at github. The citizens comments are moderated while upon completion of the deliberation, the relevant Ministry prepares a report that accompanies the draft law when submitted to Parliament for discussion and voting. *Within* AI4Deliberation, several AI features will be tested in specific deliberations. For example, we will experiment with the Summarisation functionality of AI for deliberation comments. In the first mega-sprint, we will check AI Summarisation functionality in previous deliberations and compare the AI results with the results humans had produced manually. The same will be performed for all AI features, e.g. opinion and argument extraction, fact checking etc. In the second mega-sprint we will be able to integrate AI features in law deliberations and test the results internally from technicians and administrators. In the third mega-sprint, we expect to launch law deliberations to the general public and evaluate the results by both citizens and public servants.

Fig. 4. The opengov.gr platform

Pilot 2. International deliberation on Long Covid (debategraph.org)

DebateGraph is an award-winning collaborative cloud-based platform designed to help people work together to identify, explore and understand the salient dimensions (e.g. actors, arguments, evidence) of complex situations (Fig. 5). Salient dimensions can be interrelated resulting in a map and can be annotated with e.g., text descriptions, videos, pictures. DebateGraph has hosted deliberations in over 100 countries in various fields

e.g., health, group facilitation and public consultation. There is no limit to the number of people who can collaborate on maps making it ideal for mass deliberations. *Within* AI4Deliberation, DebateGraph will be enhanced with AI features and support an international deliberation on the societal impacts of Long Covid (impacted over 65 million people globally). Many citizens afflicted by Long Covid, and their families, feel neglected and have begun to organize active communities online to accelerate societal understanding and hasten effective policy responses. In this context, the pilot aims to develop a dynamically updated deliberation graph for Long Covid including: the evidence underlying its characteristics; the personal, societal and economic implications; potential policy responses; arguments. The deliberation graph will be created/updated using a combination of human curation and AI augmentation involving various UK and international stakeholders such as patient groups, scientists, health professionals, and policy makers. Two main goals are to: i) experiment with a positive feedback loop in which the human curation of the graph enhances the signal-to-noise ratio arising from the machine reading of the relevant literature and the machine reading, in turn, accelerates the human curation of the graph, and ii) create an open knowledge graph of Long Covid as a shared public good that can inform public deliberations globally.

Fig. 5. The debategraph platform

Pilot 3. National level deliberation on Climate Change Adaptation Plan (ActionAid Italy)

The pilot is based on the implementation of a national-scale deliberative process regarding the National Climate Change Adaptation Plan (PNACC), that has been approved (January '24) by the Italian Government and is a guiding tool for the planning and implementation of adaptation actions. The deliberative process will develop in analyzing and finding recommendations on specific elements of the Plan, and its derived application (e.g., environmental policies). The deliberative path to be followed comprises the following phases: i) Information & learning, ii) Deliberation and iii) Proposals definition. AAIT has already developed a similar deliberative path without a deep use of technologies. The path was applied in 2019 for Disaster Risk Management employing mainly physical channels (workshops) to engage citizens and experts. This process resulted in recommendations on relevant public policies. A website

(#Sicuriperdavvero) was used mainly to promote content emerging from physical discussions. However, the website provides mechanisms for user feedback (voting, comments). Comments must be approved before going public. This mechanism creates a flow of comments that are visible and traceable to those who access the site, which fuels and nourishes the contents debate. *Within* AI4Deliberation, we aim at exploring the potential of AI tools integrated at a deliberative digital platform not only providing the possibility of displaying and disseminating text content but also video discussions or other means. The innovation will support the development of an online deliberation path (compared to the existing physical path) examining the use of AI to promote more inclusive deliberation.

Pilot 4. Local - city-level deliberation at the Bamberg smart city

Case 1: Top-Down Citizen Participation (Bamberg.gestalten.de). So far, digital citizen participation in Bamberg city in Germany follows a top-down approach. On a Consul-based platform the municipality regularly introduces topics to solicit corresponding input from the residents. To ensure that only actual citizens of Bamberg can participate (no bots or fake accounts) a comparison with the resident registration directory is performed. Various issues, such as the redesign and change of use of public spaces or the drafting of a self-imposed municipal data policy, have already been discussed on this platform. *Within* AI4Deliberation the use of various AI features could be discussed on this platform e.g., fact-checking. We will also test and evaluate the usage of the selected AI features e.g., test whether AI can mitigate misinformation and disinformation in municipal dialogue, thus creating an evidence-based foundation for the discussion.

Case 2: Bottom-Up Citizen Participation: An engagement platform is currently under development and will be introduced within another national ongoing project. This platform, tailored to local needs, aims to change the participation process and follow a bottom-up principle. Citizens will be able to freely present and discuss their concerns within the community and with the administration. In addition, some enabling functions will be incorporated, allowing citizens to take proactive measures regarding their pain points. *Within* AI4Deliberation, we will test the effects of AI applications on local platforms. We will also examine whether the use of AI can influence the attractiveness of local engagement platforms. In this context, the possibility of using AI to bridge the digital divide will be explored. This provides an opportunity to test how functional and beneficial AI applications can be in small-scale networks. Since this platform is still in development, we expect the two projects to collaborate and we aim to feed AI4Deliberation results to this platform as well.

Fig. 6. The Bamberg platform

7 Expected Results and Impact

The main target groups of the project include:

- Public authorities, NGOs and civil societies engaged in or planning deliberations.
- Political scientists focused on deliberative democracy.
- Youth and other citizens involved in pilot projects.
- AI feature providers exploring new market opportunities.

The expected results include:

- Integration of multimodal AI and gamification in deliberation process designs.
- Development of practical guides, roadmaps and training materials for public authorities.
- Enhancement of an existing open-source platform to accommodate multimodal, gamified AI deliberations.
- Enhancement of two existing deliberation platforms with multimodal, gamified AI features.
- Availability of AI features supporting deliberation via APIs.
- Novel methods to assess acceptance and trust in AI-assisted deliberations.
- Establishment of a deliberation Knowledge Graph with structured, high-quality content.
- Formulation of policy recommendations for integrating AI into deliberative processes. Collection of empirical data on AI use in deliberations in both test and real-world settings.

The expected impact includes:

Societal: More participatory citizens (particularly amongst youngsters) hence more active and inclusive citizenship.

Governments: Increased trust to rule-of-law based institutions by citizens. Better democratic governance as AI-enabled deliberations will increase the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of institutions as perceived by citizens.

Economic/Technological: New market for AI in the public sector (mass deliberations).

Scientific: New use of AI technologies to support video-based, gamified, mass deliberations.

8 Conclusions and Future Work

Artificial Intelligence has the potential to dramatically change the landscape of public deliberations. For the first time, mass deliberations are technically feasible. More than that, new features are possible in online deliberations that were never available before. The ability of summarizing the view of others, the ability to translate text from one language to another, the ability to fact-check content, the ability to communicate via different modals as some only of the many available with the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI). However, the adoption of AI is not without its challenges. These range from purely technical to organizational and to legal and ethical.

The AI4Deliberation is a 3-year project funded by the European Union in order to address these challenges (www.ai4dproject.eu). The project aims to provide robust, ethical AI tools and comprehensive guidance to assist governments in institutionalising, using and evaluating multimodal, gamified, mass deliberations. In this paper, we presented the objectives, overall approach, pilots, expected results, and impact of the project.

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